

1 V20I

● V
● I

- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapiini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 V20I

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 V20I

V
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shallow
intermediate
deep
NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 V20I

● V
● I

■ shallow
■ intermediate
■ deep
■ NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12